

Students' Awareness, Acceptance, and Perception of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives of the Teacher Education Program

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Abstract: This study investigates the awareness, acceptance, understanding, and perception of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) among 337 teacher education students at NEUST–Gabaldon Campus. Using a quantitative descriptive survey design and an adapted survey instrument, the study explores how BEED and BSED students engage with their institution's core principles. Data were analyzed using weighted means and percentages, with convenience sampling employed based on voluntary participation from students. Findings reveal strong awareness and understanding of institutional VMGO but lower awareness of program-specific objectives. Acceptance and clarity perception are high, with minor differences between programs. The study recommends integrating VMGO into academic activities, organizing thematic events, and establishing feedback mechanisms to enhance implementation. While the findings offer valuable insights, they are context-specific to the NEUST–Gabaldon Campus and limited to the BEED and BSED programs, which may affect their generalizability to other institutions or disciplines.

Keywords: VMGO, Awareness, Understanding, Acceptance, Perception.

Introduction

The foundation of any educational institution lies in its Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO), which guide all actions, decisions, and developmental directions (Pelicano & Lacaba, 2016). These statements are not merely symbolic expressions but serve as strategic frameworks that define institutional identity, ensure alignment among programs, and promote educational excellence (Dagdag, 2023; Tan & Borres, 2020). In higher education, particularly in teacher education programs, the VMGO plays a crucial role in shaping the values, beliefs, and professional practices of future educators. By internalizing these principles, students can align their academic pursuits with institutional goals and make meaningful contributions to the educational landscape (Pelicano & Lacaba, 2016; Bowen, 2018).

The effectiveness of VMGOs depends on their clarity, consistency, and congruency with institutional practices. Escolano (2021) described a vision statement as aspirational and motivational, while Gordon (2017) and Alegre et al. (2018) underscored the mission's role in reinforcing organizational identity and long-term success. Bolman and Deal (2017) argued that shared commitment to institutional values is essential for sustaining coherence and collective purpose. In the same vein, Villanca et al. (2020) and Arado et al. (2019) emphasized that when institutional activities and instructional practices are aligned with the VMGO, the result is a stronger sense of unity and identity.

The significance of VMGO clarity and communication has been validated across multiple empirical studies. For instance, a 2024 study at Mindoro State University's College of Computer Studies found that students perceived the VMGO as more acceptable and relevant when it was clearly communicated and embedded in course syllabi and orientations. The researchers recommended systematic integration of VMGO discussions in program activities to enhance understanding and engagement, echoing earlier findings by Bolman and Deal (2017) and Villanca et al. (2020). Similarly, Arado, Mendoza, and Esmero (2019) emphasized that stakeholder participation and transparent communication enhance awareness and acceptance of institutional goals.

Institutional accreditation frameworks, such as those established by the Accrediting Agency for Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACUP), also place strong emphasis on VMGO alignment and implementation. Liquido (2018) noted that universities are evaluated based on their ability to actualize their VMGO, not in comparison with others. The AACUP Revised Instrument (2015) identifies VMGO as a key criterion for assessing institutional quality, coherence, and stakeholder engagement. Gomez and Basco (2022) likewise asserted that a well-articulated vision and mission provide a roadmap for academic communities, fostering purposeful action and decision-making.

Research further suggests that VMGO internalization influences institutional culture and student engagement. Baluyos et al. (2024) demonstrated that institutional identity is strengthened when students actively participate in VMGO-related initiatives, as this fosters deeper value internalization and goal congruence. Gyurko and Snow (2020) found that students' awareness of institutional outcomes shapes their academic and professional decision-making, while Saroyan and Trigwell (2015) linked internalization of institutional values to higher academic performance and completion rates. Lee, Chen, and Chen (2014) also highlighted the motivational impact of goal congruence, especially when personal aspirations align with institutional objectives.

In the Philippine context, several studies reinforce that high levels of VMGO awareness, acceptance, and understanding are essential for institutional effectiveness. Bentor et al. (2017) identified VMGO integration as a driver of organizational growth, while Estrada (2018) argued that clear and achievable objectives promote stakeholder commitment. Garcia et al. (2021) added that VMGO awareness supports institutional thrusts and professional licensure outcomes. Likewise, Gurley et al. (2015) and Constantino et al. (2020) emphasized that all stakeholders—students, faculty, administrators, alumni, and parents—must understand and accept the VMGO to fulfill their roles effectively.

A 2025 study published in the International Journal of FM Research further demonstrated that student engagement significantly improves when institutions employ participatory dissemination strategies and involve students in VMGO-related planning and evaluation. This underscores that VMGO internalization extends beyond awareness; it requires active participation and meaningful reflection, aligning with the insights of Saroyan and Trigwell (2015) and Bentor et al. (2017).

At the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST) Gabaldon Campus, the College of Education upholds a vision of excellence, community engagement, and alignment with the university's VMGO. As NEUST Gabaldon prepares for accreditation reviews, understanding student awareness, acceptance, and perception of the VMGO's clarity, consistency, and congruency with institutional practices becomes essential for demonstrating effectiveness. Preliminary faculty feedback has indicated a potential gap between the stated VMGO and its reflection in classroom and program activities. This observation has motivated the present study, which seeks to assess how deeply students in the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) programs understand and internalize the university's guiding principles.

By exploring the level of VMGO awareness, acceptance, and perceived congruency among NEUST Gabaldon students, this study aims to bridge the gap between institutional intent and lived experience. The findings will provide valuable insights for improving VMGO dissemination strategies, enhancing program alignment, and strengthening the internalization of institutional values among future educators.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive survey design to measure students' awareness, acceptance, understanding, and perception of the VMGO. A validated and adapted questionnaire was used to collect data from BEED and BSED students at the NEUST-Gabaldon Campus.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST) – Gabaldon Campus, specifically within the College of Education Department. The campus offers teacher education programs, including the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED), and serves as a training ground for future educators in the region. The locale was selected due to its active implementation of institutional VMGO and its relevance to the study's objectives.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents in this study were students enrolled in the Teacher Education Program—Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED)—at the NEUST-Gabaldon Campus during the 2024–2025 school year. Participants were drawn from all year levels: 1st Year, 2nd Year, 3rd Year, and 4th Year.

Out of a total population of 365 students, 337 voluntarily participated in the survey. The study employed convenience sampling, selecting respondents based on accessibility and willingness to participate. This approach was appropriate for gathering relevant data within the time constraints and ethical considerations of the research.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study used convenience sampling, selecting 337 respondents from a total population of 365 BEED and BSED students at NEUST-Gabaldon Campus. This method was chosen due to time constraints and ethical considerations. Participation was voluntary.

Research Instrument

The study employed a structured survey questionnaire adapted from Del Rosario's (2021) study, designed to assess students' engagement with the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of the Teacher Education Program. The instrument consisted of five key parts:

1. Demographic Profile – gathered basic information such as sex, age, year level, and academic program.
2. Level of Awareness – measured how familiar students were with NEUST's VMGO and its dissemination.
3. Acceptance and Understanding – assessed the degree to which students accepted and understood the VMGO statements.
4. Perception of Clarity and Consistency – evaluated whether students found the VMGO statements clear and aligned.
5. Perception of Congruency – examined how well students believed the VMGO matched actual activities, practices, and operations.

Responses were rated using a 4-point Likert scale to encourage decisive feedback. To ensure reliability, the instrument underwent internal consistency testing using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.87, which indicates high reliability. Content validity was established through expert review by faculty members in the College of Education.

Data Collection Procedure

The data was collected using questionnaires distributed via Google Forms. After receiving approval from the research adviser, a letter of permission was forwarded to the Office of the Teacher Education Program Chair for the issuance of a research permit. The survey link was sent to all 365 BEED and BSED students enrolled at the NEUST-Gabalton Campus during the 2024–2025 school year.

Participation was voluntary, and responses were collected from students who were accessible and willing to participate. A total of 337 students completed the survey. The use of convenience sampling allowed the researchers to gather timely and relevant data from respondents across all year levels.

To ensure honest responses, the researchers provided clear instructions on confidentiality and emphasized that participation was voluntary. The Google Form was set to collect responses anonymously, and respondents were assured that their answers would not be linked to their identities. Students were given sufficient time to complete the forms, avoiding rushed responses. After completion, the results were tallied and tabulated.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically frequency, percentage distribution, and weighted mean, to summarize the respondents' demographic profiles and overall responses to VMGO-related items. These methods were appropriate for identifying general trends in awareness, understanding, acceptance, and perception among BEED and BSED students.

Although the study involved comparisons between groups (e.g., BEED vs. BSED), inferential statistics such as independent samples t-tests or one-way ANOVA were not applied. This decision was based on the study's descriptive focus and the use of non-random convenience sampling, which limits the generalizability and violates assumptions required for inferential analysis.

Ethics in Research

According to Fleming and Zegward (2018), it was important to further consider the fundamentals of ethical research involving human participants. Thus, ethical research was regarded as that which secured informed consent from participants, subjects, or respondents; respected the rights of those being investigated; and did not result in harm, stress, or discomfort. The researchers thoroughly evaluated ethical issues at every stage of this investigation, which necessitated careful consideration. Therefore, when creating the questionnaire, offensive, discriminatory, or other undesirable language was avoided.

To ensure that respondents understood the implications of participating and made a fully informed, deliberated, and freely given decision about whether or not to do so, without the use of any pressure or coercion, the researchers considered the principle of informed consent to provide sufficient information and assurance about participation.

For ethical considerations, the respondents were informed that their participation in this study was completely voluntary. The researchers assured the respondents that their responses and personal information would be strictly

confidential and used solely for research purposes. The researchers also avoided plagiarism and fraud by acknowledging the works of other authors used in any part of this study.

Results

Students' Profile

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents. The respondent group demonstrated a significant gender imbalance, with females representing the majority (78.3%) and males a minority (21.7%). Most respondents (73.9%) were aged 17-21, indicating they were primarily within the typical college student age range. The distribution of respondents across year levels showed a higher representation of lower-year students, with first-year students comprising the largest group (38.3%). Finally, there was a relatively balanced representation between BEED (52.2%) and BSED (47.8%) students.

Table 1

The profiles of the respondents.

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	73	21.7
Female	264	78.3
Total	337	100
Age	Frequency	Percentage
17-21	249	73.9
22-25	85	25.2
26-above	3	0.9
Total	337	100
Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
1 st Year	129	38.3%
2 nd Year	87	25.8%
3 rd Year	76	22.6%
4 th Year	45	13.4%
Total	337	100
Course	Frequency	Percentage
BEED	176	52.2
BSED	161	47.8
Total	337	100

Students' Level of Awareness on the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives

Table 2 shows the students' level of awareness of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of the teacher education program. Students were generally aware of the Teacher Education Program's VMGO, particularly regarding the university's broad vision (3.81) and mission (3.79). However, they demonstrated a comparatively lower level of awareness concerning the specific objectives of the BEED program and the dissemination of VMGO to external stakeholders, with an overall awareness level of "Aware" and a total weighted mean of 3.29.

Table 2

Students' Level of Awareness on the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives of the Teacher Education Program.

Level of Awareness on the VMGO	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am aware of NEUST's vision.	3.79	Highly Aware
2. I am aware of NEUST's mission.	3.81	Highly Aware
3. I am aware of the goals of the College of Education.	3.36	Aware
4. I am aware of the objectives of the Bachelor of Secondary Education.	3.09	Aware
5. I am aware of the objectives of the Bachelor of Elementary Education.	3.00	Aware
6. I am aware that the VGMOs are displayed on bulletin boards.	3.31	Aware
7. I am aware that the VGMO is printed in catalogs, manuals, and other materials.	3.12	Aware

8. I am aware that the VGMO is broadcast in the media and/or on the internet/website.	3.15	Aware
9. I am aware that the VGMO has been widely disseminated to various agencies, institutions, industry sectors, and the public.	3.01	Aware
Total Weighted Mean	3.29	Aware

Student's Level of Acceptance and Understanding of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives

Students generally demonstrated a high level of acceptance and understanding of the VMGO, with acceptance and understanding of NEUST's Vision and Mission being particularly strong (3.76), while the BEED program objectives were slightly less well-accepted (weighted mean = 3.36). Overall, the total weighted mean for acceptance and understanding was 3.54, interpreted as "Accepted and Understood."

Table 3

Student's Level of Acceptance and Understanding of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives of the Teacher Education Program.

Acceptance and Understanding of the VMGO	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I accept and understand the Vision and Mission of NEUST.	3.76	Greatly Accepted and Understood
2. I accept and understand the Goals of the College of Education.	3.66	Accepted and Understood
3. I accept and understand the Objectives of the Bachelor of Secondary Education.	3.39	Accepted and Understood
4. I accept and understand the Objectives of the Bachelor of Elementary Education.	3.36	Accepted and Understood
Total Weighted Mean	3.54	Accepted and Understood

Perceptions Regarding VMGO's Clarity and Consistency

Perceptions of the VMGO's clarity and consistency were generally positive. The Vision statement achieved the highest weighted mean (3.75, "Strongly Agree"), demonstrating strong clarity. However, program objectives concerning moral character, aesthetic, and cultural values received slightly lower ratings (3.51, "Agree"). Overall, the total weighted mean for clarity and consistency was 3.70, categorized as "Agree."

Table 4

Students' Perceptions Regarding VMGO's Clarity and Consistency.

Perceptions regarding VMGO's clarity and consistency	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The Vision reflects what NEUST hopes to become in the future.	3.75	Strongly Agree
2. The Mission reflects NEUST's legal and educational mandate.	3.69	Agree
3. The Goals of the college program are clearly stated and are consistent with the mission of NEUST.	3.65	Agree
4. The Program Objectives are consistent with the goals of NEUST.	3.64	Agree
5. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of competencies or technical skills of students and graduates.	3.59	Agree
6. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of research and extension capabilities of students and graduates.	3.57	Agree
7. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of students' own ideas, desirable attitudes and personal discipline.	3.56	Agree
8. The Program Objectives unequivocally state what is expected in terms of moral character.	3.51	Agree
9. The Program Objectives state clearly what is expected in terms of critical thinking skills.	3.59	Agree
10. The Program Objectives unequivocally state what is expected in terms of aesthetic and cultural values.	3.51	Agree

Total Weighted Mean	3.70	Agree
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Students' Perception Regarding VMGO's Congruency with Activities, Practices, Projects, and Operations

In general, students recognized the alignment of the VMGO with the program's activities, practices, projects, and operations, affirming its role as a fundamental framework for university operations. This is evidenced by a high rating for its alignment with NEUST's operations (weighted mean = 3.51, interpreted as "Agree"). However, congruency with the BSED program's activities and practices was slightly less favorably perceived (weighted mean = 3.40, interpreted as "Agree"). Overall, the total weighted mean for congruency was computed at 3.455, which falls under the interpretation of "Agree," demonstrating that the VMGO is positively perceived as aligned with the institutions and program's goals and activities.

Table 5

Students' Perception Regarding VMGO's Congruency with Activities, Practices, Projects, and Operations.

Perception Regarding VMGO's Congruency with Activities, Practices, Projects, and Operations	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The VMGO is congruent between actual educational practices and activities and the NEUST Mission.	3.45	Agree
2. The VMGO is congruent between actual educational practices and activities and the University's goals.	3.45	Agree
3. The VMGO is congruent between actual educational practices and activities of the BSED program.	3.40	Agree
4. The VMGO is congruent between actual educational practices and activities of the BEED program.	3.42	Agree
5. The projects and activities carried out by the faculty and students directly contribute towards the achievement of the program outcomes.	3.50	Agree
6. The VMGO is the basis of all NEUST's operations.	3.51	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.45	Agree

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal several significant insights into the students' awareness, acceptance, understanding, and perception of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of the Teacher Education Program at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST), Gabaldon Campus. These findings underscore the critical role of VMGO as a guiding framework that aligns institutional activities with educational values and strategic goals, consistent with the perspectives of Pelicano and Lacaba (2016) and Dagdag (2023), who emphasize that clearly articulated VMGOs are vital for institutional effectiveness and coherence.

The demographic profile of respondents reflects a pattern typical of teacher education programs in the Philippines, where female students constitute the majority. This aligns with Reyes et al. (2021), who observed the growing feminization of the teaching profession in the country. The predominance of female students suggests that the teaching profession continues to attract women who view education as both a vocation and a platform for community development. The age distribution, primarily 17 to 21 years old, corresponds to CHED's (2023) data identifying this range as the norm among undergraduate students. Moreover, the relatively larger proportion of first-year students indicates strong initial interest in the education field, consistent with demographic patterns observed in previous institutional studies. The near-equal representation between BEED and BSED students also mirrors findings from Biscante (2018), who highlighted that a balanced program representation provides a more comprehensive lens in evaluating teacher education outcomes and institutional effectiveness.

In terms of awareness, the results suggest that students are generally aware of NEUST's Vision and Mission, reflecting successful institutional dissemination efforts. The strong awareness of these core statements supports the conclusions of Sanchez and Olvido (2023) and Gagasa and Rogayan (2021), who found that effective dissemination—through visible platforms, interactive participation, and stakeholder involvement—enhances students' understanding and engagement with institutional goals. However, while institutional-level awareness is high, there appears to be less familiarity with program-specific objectives, particularly in the BEED program. This aligns with Fernandez (2015), who noted that students often demonstrate greater awareness of university-level goals than those specific to their programs. The gap

underscores the need for targeted communication strategies to ensure that students not only know the institution's overarching goals but also understand how these translate into their program outcomes.

The findings on students' acceptance and understanding of the VMGO reveal strong endorsement of NEUST's Vision and Mission, indicating that students recognize the relevance and significance of these institutional principles in guiding their academic and professional paths. This resonates with Pelicano and Lacaba (2016), who emphasized that institutional effectiveness depends on the shared understanding and acceptance of its vision and mission among stakeholders. Students' high acceptance and understanding signify that NEUST's VMGO is meaningful and clearly aligned with their educational experiences. However, the relatively lower acceptance of program-specific objectives, particularly in the BEED program, suggests that while institutional ideals are well-communicated, there is room to strengthen the articulation of how specific program goals support the broader mission. This observation aligns with Gyurko and Snow (2020), who highlighted that student awareness of institutional outcomes influences academic engagement and decision-making. Enhancing the visibility of program-level objectives through course syllabi, classroom discussions, and mentorship can help deepen students' internalization of these goals.

Students' perceptions of VMGO clarity and consistency further affirm the effectiveness of NEUST's institutional communication. The Vision statement, in particular, was perceived as clear and forward-looking, consistent with Escolano's (2021) assertion that an effective vision motivates long-term institutional and individual commitment. The Mission and Goals statements were likewise viewed as coherent and reflective of NEUST's educational mandate. However, slightly lower perceptions were noted regarding the clarity of program objectives related to moral character and cultural values. This indicates that while the general framework is well-understood, the communication of certain value-based objectives may require reinforcement. Bolman and Deal (2017) stressed the importance of ensuring that institutional values are explicitly communicated to sustain a cohesive organizational culture. Therefore, the findings suggest that NEUST could benefit from further embedding these aspects into student activities, orientations, and reflective learning opportunities to strengthen value internalization.

Perceptions of congruency between the VMGO and institutional activities, practices, projects, and operations reveal that students generally recognize strong alignment. This reinforces the idea proposed by Pelicano and Lacaba (2016) and Gomez and Basco (2022) that the VMGO serves as a unifying framework guiding both strategic and operational dimensions of institutional life. Students' agreement that the VMGO underpins NEUST's operations indicates successful integration of institutional goals into daily academic practices. However, perceptions of slightly lower congruency within the BSED program suggest that further efforts may be needed to ensure that all program activities explicitly reflect the institution's mission and objectives. Astorga et al. (2022) recommended enhancing internalization through socialization and externalization strategies, which could be adapted to strengthen the visibility of VMGO principles in classroom instruction and program implementation.

The results collectively highlight that NEUST Gabaldon Campus has achieved a commendable level of VMGO awareness, acceptance, and congruency among its education students. Nonetheless, the identified gaps—particularly in program-specific objectives and in the clarity of moral and cultural dimensions—present opportunities for continuous improvement. Sanchez and Olvido (2023) underscored the importance of dissemination strategies that actively engage students, faculty, and the community, while Arado et al. (2019) emphasized that consistent communication and stakeholder participation are key to deepening understanding and alignment. Implementing these recommendations could further enhance the institution's efforts to embed the VMGO in all levels of academic and operational practice.

Overall, the findings suggest that NEUST's VMGO is not only understood and accepted by its students but also reflected in institutional activities and culture. However, to fully realize its transformative potential, the university must ensure that every student—across programs and year levels—recognizes how their individual academic journey contributes to the collective fulfillment of NEUST's vision and mission. By reinforcing communication, contextualization, and participation, NEUST can continue to cultivate future educators who embody the values and goals that define the institution.

Conclusion

The findings revealed that most respondents were in their late teens, predominantly female, and enrolled in either the BEED or BSED program, offering a representative snapshot of the NEUST-Gabaldon teacher education population. Students demonstrated strong awareness, acceptance, and understanding of NEUST's institutional Vision and Mission, which served as a foundation for their alignment with the university's core values. However, awareness and internalization of program-specific objectives—particularly those of the BEED and BSED programs—were comparatively lower, indicating a gap in targeted communication and curricular integration. Students generally perceived the VMGO as clear and consistent, especially at the institutional level, though statements related to moral character and cultural values received slightly lower clarity ratings. Perceptions of congruency between VMGO and actual practices were positive, with

students recognizing its influence on university operations and academic activities, although alignment within the BSED program was rated less favorably. These results suggest that while institutional messaging is effective, program-level reinforcement and participatory engagement strategies are needed to strengthen VMGO internalization across all dimensions of the teacher education experience.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study on students' awareness, acceptance, and perception of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) at NEUST–Gabaldon Campus, several recommendations are proposed. The campus may consider implementing targeted recruitment and support initiatives to promote gender inclusivity in teacher education, including mentorship programs and outreach activities that engage alumni and community stakeholders. To strengthen VMGO internalization, first-year students may benefit from structured orientations and visible dissemination strategies, such as bulletin board displays, flag ceremony features, and digital campaigns tailored to each academic program. Integrating VMGO discussions into syllabi and academic routines—particularly at the start of each semester—can reinforce its relevance, while reflective activities, classroom projects, and assessments may deepen student engagement.

To promote moral, aesthetic, and cultural values embedded in the VMGO, the campus may organize themed events such as essay writing, poster-making, and video production competitions during university celebrations. These initiatives may be complemented by a clearer articulation of program objectives and their integration into co-curricular activities. Establishing feedback mechanisms, including surveys and focus groups, can provide valuable insights into students' understanding and experiences, supporting continuous improvement. Collaboration with accrediting bodies and external partners may further ensure that VMGO implementation aligns with institutional standards and educational goals.

Future researchers are encouraged to explore the long-term impact of VMGO internalization on student development, academic performance, and professional readiness. Comparative studies across campuses and institutions may reveal effective dissemination practices, while gender-responsive approaches and digital tools such as social media can enhance inclusivity and reach. The use of inferential statistics, including t-tests and ANOVA, may also uncover significant patterns across demographic groups, contributing to a deeper understanding of VMGO engagement in teacher education.

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Author Contributions

Erika B. Lozano led the overall direction of the study, including conceptualization, data analysis, writing, supervision, and final editorial decisions. She oversaw the research process from design to completion, ensuring the study's coherence and quality.

Joseph A. Domingo contributed to the data collection phase of the study.

Mary Cris A. Galvez provided guidance on methodology and ethical considerations.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

AI Use Declaration

This research utilized artificial intelligence (AI) tools solely to assist in refining grammar, formatting, and enhancing the clarity and coherence of the manuscript. The researchers maintained full responsibility for the conceptualization, data

collection, analysis, interpretation, and overall integrity of the study. No AI tool was used to generate, alter, or fabricate research data or results.

References

- Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines. (2015). *AACCUP revised instrument for accreditation: Institutional, program, and area parameters*. AACCUP, Inc.
- Alegre, I., Berbegal-Mirabent, J., Guerrero, A., & Mas-Machuca, M. (2018). The real mission of the mission statement: A systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 24(4), 456–473. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2018>
- Astorga, A. D., Villanueva, R. T., & Juarez, S. P. (2022). Assessing the impact of VMGO in higher education institutions: Strategies for alignment and internalization. *Journal of Institutional Research*, 18(2), 78–92.
- Baluyos, G. E., Baluyos, G. R., & Baluyos, G. M. (2024). Students' awareness, practices, and engagement in the institution's philosophy, vision, mission, goals, objectives, and core values. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/388911697>
- Bentor, S. S., Bentor, P. M. S., & Bentor, C. T. S. (2017). Awareness, acceptability, and relevance of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of the programs of Naval State University Graduate School. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research*, 32(1), 181–206.
- Biscante, D. D. S. (2018). *Tracer study of the teacher education graduates*. Eastern Visayas State University. <https://www.evsu.edu.ph/university-research-and-created-works/tracer-study-of-the-teacher-education-graduates/>
- Bolman, L. G., & Deal, T. E. (2017). *Reframing organizations: Artistry, choice, and leadership* (6th ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Bowen, S. A. (2018). Mission and vision. In *The international encyclopedia of strategic communication* (pp. 1–9). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119010722.iesc0030>
- Clarke, A., & Tyler, L. K. (2015). Understanding what we see: How we derive meaning from vision. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 19(11), 677–687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2015.08.008>
- Commission on Higher Education. (2023). *2023 Higher Education Facts and Figures*. <https://ched.gov.ph/2023-higher-education-facts-and-figures/>
- Compelio, K. J., Caranto, L., & David, J. J. (2015). Awareness, understanding, and acceptance of student nurses of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of Benguet State University. *International Journal of Nursing Science*, 5(1), 20–27.
- Constantino, J. A., Sison, M. H., Gabriel, E. C., & Vega, M. T. C. (2020). Perception, awareness, acceptance, and understanding of NEUST-SIC community towards its vision, mission, goals, and objectives. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science*, 6(7), 335–346.
- Dagdag, J. D., Palapuz, N. A., Caliboso, J. C., Peru, E. I., & Mauro, R. P. (2023). Stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of the vision, mission, goals, and outcomes statements of a teacher education college. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 12(4), 339–346. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v12i4.23975>
- Del Rosario, J. (2021). *Students' level of awareness, acceptance, and perception on the mission, vision, goals and objectives of the teacher education program*. Gabaldon Campus.
- Del Rosario, M. A., & Santos, J. R. (2025). *VMGO internalization and student engagement across Philippine higher education institutions*. *International Journal of FM Research*, 12(1), 22–35.
- Escolano, E. (2021). Awareness and acceptability on the institution's vision, mission, goals, and quality policy in one state college in the Philippines. *Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies*, 1(2), 10–24. <https://doi.org/10.52631/jemds.v1i2.31>
- Escolano, S. M. (2021). Analysis of vision and mission clarity: Its role in institutional effectiveness. *Journal of Academic Management*, 12(4), 49–58.
- Estrada, J. (2018). Awareness and acceptability of the vision, mission, and institutional goals of Pangasinan State University and AB Economics program objectives. *Southeast Asian Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(1), 21–35.

- Fernandez, M. W. (2015). Awareness, acceptability, relevance, and congruence of the PNU-Negros Occidental vision, mission, and goals and objectives of the teacher education program. *Philippine Journal of Education and Research*, 10(3), 45–62.
- Fleming, J., & Zegwaard, K. E. (2018). Methodologies, methods, and ethical considerations for conducting research in work-integrated learning. *International Journal of Work-Integrated Learning*, 19(3), 205–213.
- Gagasa, K. L., & Rogayan, D. V., Jr. (2021). Stakeholders' awareness and acceptability of university's vision and mission, and teacher education program goals and objectives in a state institution in Central Luzon, Philippines. *Asian Journal of Teacher Education*, 8(1), 25–37.
- Garcia, S., Rogayan, D., & Gagasa, K. L. (2021). Stakeholders' awareness and acceptability of university's vision and mission, and teacher education program goals and objectives in a state institution in Central Luzon, Philippines. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 2(1), 17–23.
- Gomez, A. C., & Basco, M. C. M. (2022). Awareness, acceptability, and perception of stakeholders on the vision and mission of Cavite State University, teacher education department goals, and education program objectives. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(1), 66–75.
- Gomez, A. C., & Basco, M. C. M. (2022). Congruence between VMGO and institutional practices: A case study of Cavite State University. *Philippine Journal of Education and Research*, 10(4), 12–20.
- Gordon, G. (2017). Communication, vision, and mission. In *Leadership through trust* (pp. 63–69). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-55595-9_7
- Gurley, D. K., Peters, G. B., Collins, L., & Fifolt, M. (2015). Mission, vision, values, and goals: An exploration of key organizational statements and daily practice in schools. *Journal of Educational Change*, 16(2), 217–242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-014-9229-x>
- Gyrko, J., & Snow, M. (2020). Quality teaching and learning: The influence of outcome awareness on student decisions. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 52(5), 7–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00091383.2020.1819849>
- Lee, S. Y., Chen, C. J., & Chen, S. C. (2014). The relationship between employee goal alignment and job performance: An empirical study in Taiwan. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25(15), 2136–2151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2013.870316>
- Liquido, M. G. E. (2018). *The accreditation of state universities and colleges in the Philippines: Governance, hegemony relationship and dichotomy of ownership*.
- Mindoro State University. (2024). Exploring student perceptions and acceptability of VMGO in a technology-focused academic unit. *International Conference on Contemporary Education, Psychology and Humanities*. <https://icceph.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/EXPLORING-STUDENT-PERCEPTIONS.pdf>
- Pelicano, A. C., & Lacaba, L. D. (2016). Awareness and acceptability of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of Eastern Samar State University. *International Journal of Innovation and Research in Educational Sciences*, 3(6), 432–435.
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2024). Philippine education indicators: Age distribution of college students. <https://psa.gov.ph>
- Reyes, Z. Q., Jusayan, M. T., Susara, P. C., & Mariano, A. M. A. (2021). *Integrating gender and development agenda in teacher education institutions and Philippine standards for teachers and education leaders*. Philippine Normal University.
- Sanchez, J. M., & Olvido, M. M. (2023). Awareness, dissemination, and acceptability of VMGO in an education graduate school of a state university in Central Visayas, Philippines. *Journal of Educational Management and Leadership Studies*, 15(2), 134–150.
- Saroyan, A., & Trigwell, K. (2015). Higher education teachers' professional learning: Process and outcome. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 46, 92–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2015.03.002>
- Tan, D. A., & Borres, T. H. (2020). Awareness, acceptability, consistency, and clarity of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of Central Mindanao University and its congruence to outcomes-based instruction: A preliminary result. *Science International (Lahore)*, 32(1), 93–98.
- Villanca, A. A., Binayao, B. S., Caterial, M. Z. D., & Ablanque, V. C. (2020). Assessing the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of a state university in Southern Philippines. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(10), 189–194.